

A Conceptual Study on Total Quality Management from Management Theories and Management Techniques

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Abstract

Management, which is a concept as old as the history of humanity, gained a scientific character with Taylor's book "Principles of Scientific Management" in the first quarter of the 1900s, and then continued its change by enriching it with research, assumptions and experiences based on cyclical developments. The management approaches, which are generally examined in four basic stages as the classic Period, the Neo-Classical Period, the Modern Period and the Post-Modern Period, have become an interdisciplinary discipline since the Neo-Classical School, where the importance of the human element in businesses is understood. Of the first years of the scientific management approach, Taylor, Fayol and Weber talked about inefficiency, not doing things properly, and the difficulties caused by traditional methods; They tried to develop methods to increase productivity. Classical Management attributed the most important reason for inefficiency to the management approach. The traditional management approach with black order has been seen as the cause of waste. When the weaknesses in the managerial field were combined with the wrong perspective on the human element productivity could not be mentioned. The importance of the human factor in production was understood during the Neoclassical School period. It was realized in the famous Hawthorne Experiments, performed in the period between 1924-1932, that behaviors and attitudes are effective in increasing work efficiency. Social Psychologist Elton Mayo essentially wanted to test the theorems of classical understanding and revealed the importance of the human factor. Afterwards, various theorems have developed in the managerial lane with modern management understandings. Theories such as systems approach, contingency theory and resource dependency have attracted attention on the necessity of evaluating business together with their environment. Total Quality Management, on the other hand, was developed on the basis that the concept of quality should be approached as a whole and adopted that the human element should be at the center of the understanding of quality. Of this study, management and management approaches were

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evaluated theoretically , the historical process of management was examined , some theorists who contributed to the development and scientific qualification of management were included , and the assumptions of theorists were tried to be examined . Of addition , the main elements related to the basic management techniques have been discussed with short titles , Total Quality Management, one of these techniques , has been investigated with its conceptual aspects and its importance for business has been revealed .

Keywords : *Management, Manager, Organization , Management Approaches , Quality , Total Quality Management.*

1. Introduction

The Concept of Management and Its Historical Development

Management appears as a necessary concept in all activities related to production without distinction between goods and services. When we look at history, the oldest management practices were formed in the state, tribe and community management and defense, in other words military organizations; entrepreneurship in the field of economy and managerial practices in this field developed much later (Nişancı, 2015:258-260) .

Management is to supply coordination and coordination between organizational and managerial functions to achieve organizational goals. Management, which expresses the activities to ensure cooperation and harmony in the realization of the aims, is conducted by more than one person . This concept expresses the coordination between organizational and managerial functions. Management is an act of administration and an economic, technical and social activity (Tutar, 2005:21).

Öztaş defines management as an activity performed by managers in organizations (Öztaş, 2017:19). Fişek also used the concept of administration to name the concealing purpose of the state and the mechanism that implements these goals . In addition, Fişek states that the intellectual development of management focuses on two main themes. The first of these main themes is the solution of general management problems in a universal framework and in line with theoretical criteria, without distinction of public or private sector; the second is social life, especially economy, education, defense and science, etc. of different segments It requires an interdisciplinary perspective that stipulates the necessity of benefiting from self -management

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(Fişek, 2015:31-32). In the simplest terms, Yildirim describes management as getting people to work; It defines it as "the whole of planning, organizing, directing and controlling functions for the realization of organizational goals" (Yıldırım, 2014:121).

After these descriptive concepts related to management, when the historical course of management practices is examined, it is seen that it goes back to the date of the first article. The Sumerians ruled human societies under the leadership of priests. When the clay tablets are examined, it is seen that the priests wrote the administrative rules and principles. On the other hand, when the Egyptian civilization is examined, it is revealed that the irrigation systems and the Egyptian pyramids were built with a great workforce organization and management success. Hammurabi, on the other hand, enacted laws that set an example for the rulers and guide the lawmakers even today to rule Babylon (Tengelimoğlu, Atilla, Bektaş, 2018:101,102) .

Administrative issues were also met in the findings of the first settlements in ancient Chinese civilizations . Much later, it is seen that these contributions continue with work at the group or individual level. For example, while Farabi focuses on the characteristics of leaders in one of his works, it is revealed that Ghazali refers to the distinguishing features of managers. However, the beginning of the training of executives, that is, managers, is a much more recent development. Opened in Paris, France in 1819, ESCP stands out as the world's first business school. Afterwards, in 1881, the University of Pennsylvania was set up in the USA and education began. In addition, Syracuse opened in the USA in 1926 with the 18th century European Camerism in continental Europe. The University 's Department of Public Administration was among the first modern schools to train public administrators. The main argument of modern schools has drawn attention mainly as a matter needed by the state administration. For example, Enderun School, which had been functioning for many years in the Ottoman Empire, also served as a higher administration school. Enderun is one of the firsts of the tradition that systematically trains political leaders (Fişek, 2015:19-21; Nişancı, 2015:261). After the Industrial Revolution, starting from the 19th century, the world first experienced the organizational revolution and then the managerial change process (Öztaş, 2017:66).

Figure 1. Development of Management Thinking

Source: Bergeron , Pierre G .; *La Gestion dynamic* ; gaeten morin editor.

Montreal,Paris ,Casablanca;1995:39; Transferred by: Nişancı , 2015:262.

2. THEORIES OF MANAGEMENT

2.1 Classical School (Classical Management)

Classical school theories did not deal with how to market products and services, but rather focused on how they should be produced. There are three basic theories of classical management thought. Scientific Management, Management Process and Bureaucracy constitute these basic theories. The classical school has features such as centralism, unity of management, division of labor, authority and responsibility. However, it is possible to summarize the philosophy of the classical management theory with the following items (Cengiz, 2013:8):

- Efficiency can be increased by preventing waste and losses.
- An ideal organizational structure can be created based on the criterion of universality of management .
- The organization has a closed system, and the same principles and processes can be applied in all organizations.

- In the success of the organization, the system is important, not the people.

2.1.1 Taylor and Scientific Management

When we look at the views of the French scientist Rene Descartes that include his principles about science, it can be clearly seen that his third rule is also valid for management. As Descartes states that what can be seen clearly or thought to be obtained definitively should be researched and that science can only be accessed in this way (Descartes, 2016); Of course, the fact that the management has a scientific process has developed and realized because of observations and research. Although it has a history of approximately 1 century based on science, the administration has made great progress in a brief time.

With the discovery that it is important for businesses or organizations to use existing resources effectively; It has been seen that studies on the future of business, manager and management have increased rapidly. Basically, the factor that triggered this process was inefficiency. This element made history for the first time by a Frenchman, JR Perronet , in 1760, with the determination of the procedures needed for pin production and the development of work measurement for it. From this point of view, it is possible to say that the development of work measurement owes to the scientific management school and to its founder Taylor (Timur, 2005:139).

Scientific Management, written by Taylor , was published in 1911 and added a scientific dimension to management. Taylor, a mechanical engineer, refers in the first part of his book to the speech of United States President Roosevelt to the governors at the White House. Taylor argues that, rather than a well-managed resources, a much larger waste is mainly due to the inability of manpower to be well-managed (Taylor, 2016). Engineer Taylor's observations on inefficiency, which causes great losses in the national economy as well as in organizations, are as follows:

- *In organizations, things are inefficient, and it is about doing better.*
- *Employees want to work less and there is a problem of laziness. It is possible to cut systematic laziness by setting up a good system.*
- *abilities , abilities and expertise are not taken into consideration in recruitment and promotion .*
- *Standard time for work, movements are not available.*

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- *Some of the responsibilities that the management should undertake are placed on the workers.*

Taylor aims to prevent inefficiency and waste that affects the future of organizations. It is necessary to abandon the black order or the corrupt order in management and production. Taylor suggested paying per piece and adopted the view that productivity could be measured and even increased by using time and motion study. Saying that it is possible to increase the yield, Taylor also drew attention to the methods to be applied for this.

In fact, Taylor's path is quite simple. He made observations, examined the working processes or forms and the production part of the organizations in general, including the company he worked for. As a result, he decided that there is a waste of resources due to inefficiency. Because the works are not done professionally, but amateurishly and according to certain rules. It is also managed by individuals. It is not possible to talk about rationality . The conclusion reached from these explanations is that "Scientific Management" should be applied in organizations and production should be put in a systematic order. According to Taylor, rationalizing management can solve the problem.

According to Taylor, a job can be done in quite diverse ways. But only one of these methods is superior to the others. Engineer Taylor described this superior single method as 'the only best way' or 'the only best method' . Taylor, with his "time and motion studies" that made him famous around the world, examined the movements that make up a work and the completion times (Öztaş, 2017: 97-99).

Overview of Taylor's Time and Motion Study

Production consists of repetitive movements. Taylor saw the shoveling (shoveling, stabbing, pushing, lifting, etc.) processes of the ore business . As a result, it has weeded out movements that are not essential for finishing or completing the rowing job . In addition, it has determined the standard work movements to perform the mentioned movements in the best way. These steps we are talking about constitute the movement studies of Taylorism school. To do the job better, Taylor was also interested in equipment design and designed nearly 10 types of shovels (Öztaş, 2017:97-99). In another step, Taylor measured job times to maximize productivity. Using a chronometer, Taylor also determined the completion times of the works in the enterprise and how long they could be completed. These are known as time studies. Therefore,

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time and motion studies have the essence of Taylorism. This can also be seen as a standardization.

2.1.3 Criticisms

Frederick Taylor approached organizations from a micro point of view and focused more on business than management. It has been criticized for seeing organizations as machines. Taylor, one of the founders of the classical school, suggested time and motion study and defended this and said that the important thing is productivity. However, to the workers, another criticism has been that he proposes to be paid according to their productivity, not the hours worked. According to Peter Drucker, this proposition is still something that labor unions condemn (Drucker, 2015). Scientific management, and therefore Taylorism, has made productivity growth a passion in organizations that it has mechanically evaluated and modeled. Therefore, he could only include the human phenomenon within this mechanical model (Fişek 2016:70).

2.2 Management Process (Management Process)

Fayol was on the side of Frederick Taylor's struggle against the waste caused by traditional methods and after the black order but focused entirely on management. Fayol, who created the Administrative Theory, explained the traditional management style and bad management styles as the cause of waste and inefficiency in businesses.

Fayol made observations about businesses in France, like the methods Taylor applied in the USA, and found solutions by diagnosing problems. In fact, his goal is shared with Taylor; to design a rational organizational structure based on efficiency. Unlike Taylor, Fayol increased his attention and research by focusing on the management of organizations. Fayol's book, General Industrial Management, was published in 1916. In this book, Fayol summarizes the processes required by industrial jobs as technical, commercial, financial, accounting and management jobs and states that these basic jobs are found in every organization (Fayol, 2013). Fayol, who looks at management affairs at a macro level, put forward the phenomenon of "Process in Management". He drew attention as the first person to approach this phenomenon. It is also possible to say that Fayol approaches management based on strategy (Amazigh, 2016:118-132).

2.2.1 Functions of Management

Fayol said that there are some basic functions and principles in management, and because of his long studies, he decided five basic functions. These basic functions are listed as follows:

- *Planning*
- *Organizing*
- *Orientation*
- *Coordination*
- *Check*

The principles adopted in addition to the five basic functions are also important for Fayol. The structural, procedural and outcome principles that Fayol has found are also especially important. It is possible to see these principles and their details in Figure 2.2.1 below

Figure 2.2.1 Principles Regarding Structure, Process and Results

Yapısal İlkeler	Süreç İlkeleri	Sonuçlarla İlgili İlkeler
İşbölümü	Kumanda birliği	Düzen
Yönetim birliği	Disiplin	Personel devamlılığı
Merkezcilik	Adil ve eşit muamele	İnisiyatif
Yetki ve sorumluluk	Maaş ve ücretler	Birlik ve beraberlik
Hiyerarşi ilkesi	Genel çıkarların, kişisel çıkarlara üstünlüğü	

Source: Berberoğlu, 2004:106; Reported by Sonmez, 2011:7-16.

Management functions, according to Fayol, are of immense importance in the existence of organizations, regardless of whether they are public or private. It is even possible to say that the management function has a more dominant role at the organizational level than the other functions. It is much more inclusive than it is about referral and administration. The

management function provides the organization 's compliance with other functions in the determination and implementation of its policies and it decides the future of the organization. The management function, which has a dominant function in organizations or businesses, stands out as a shared element among employees . Along with the role of managers in management and administration, participation is provided at other levels by the hierarchy by the management function (Şengül, 2007).

2.2.2 Evaluation

Although Fayol seems to be interested in managers and the functions they must implement, it is seen that he looks at the issue from the perspective of management and especially senior management. Fayol, especially the division of labor and specialization, has attached to the principles that the assignment of both responsibility and authority to the lower-level employees should be conducted in a certain discipline and order. Employees are expected to feel safe when these issues are respected. However, Fayol thinks that employees cannot be trusted (Asunakutlu , 2001).

Administrative processes are important in terms of the integrity of the business and its results. To give a recent example, businessperson Üzeyr in his memoirs, Garih mentions that the quality of the work changes depending on the managerial understanding, and this shows that this concept was not adequately understood in terms of managerial level in Turkey at that time, and even his awareness was not established. Garih describes the following incident in his memoirs: While certain facilities were being built in Incirlik, when some American experts expressed to our workers that some elements were not done correctly, our masters told the Americans that they should not worry, and they would fix it at once (Garih , 2018). As can be seen here, the concept of quality is not sufficiently settled. This state, which is met in workers or masters, also has an administrative part. From this example, it is revealed that managers are also weak in terms of management.

According to Fayol, man is lazy and busy looking for ways to avoid doing work. Bringing the employees in order is possible with strict discipline and punishment. Managers should never trust the employees at their lower levels, and they should check the work (Asunakutlu , 2001).

2.3 Bureaucracy Theory

Theory of Bureaucracy, developed by Max Weber, has a disciplinary basis and hierarchical features, as in other theorists of the classical approach, Fayol and Taylor. According to Fişek, it can be said that the bureaucracy follows a course that expresses the increasing dominance of civil servants in the society (Fişek, 2015:98-99).

Weber did not supply a definition for bureaucracy. Instead of making a specific definition, he drew an ideal type of bureaucracy by revealing the basic features and criteria . The expressions that he draws the most attention in this sense are authority, ideal type and dominance. With this, Weber mostly focused on the ideal type and made it a model (Akçakaya, 2016).

Max Weber, who had a turbulent life, could only publish his book named Social and Economic Organization Theory after his death . It is possible to say that his work is considered one of the pinnacles of social sciences.

Theory of bureaucracy, which argues that all activities implemented in businesses should be bound to written rules , it is necessary to protect impersonality . In fact, Weber says that the best method of creating this is to do the work in line with the written instructions (Yıldırım, 2014:121-267).

For Weber, as with the other founders of the Classical School , division of labor with specialization is of immense importance. The existence of an organization depends on whether there is a manager (Weber, 2017). Sociologist Max Weber seeks legitimacy in administration. According to him, there are three types of authority: traditional authority, legal-rational authority and charismatic authority. (“Industrialism and Modernization – Mass Communication Talk”) However, among these, he gave more importance to the concept of legal-rational authority than others. This is the result of Weber's ideal typing. The ideal is bureaucracy itself. It is possible to give the features of Weber's ideal bureaucracy model under the following headings:

- *Duties and authorities are predetermined in the light of certain rules.*
- *There is adherence to procedures and rules.*
- *Technical ability is available.*
- *Civil service is considered a profession.*
- *Written registration is essential.*
- *impersonality and no attachment to persons.*

On the other hand, according to Fişek, a Weberian bureaucracy is based on the thesis of "to take root firmly in society and state life" (Fişek, 2015:107).

2.3.1 Evaluation

Despite some criticisms, it is possible to say that the theory of bureaucracy keeps its importance. Impersonality, adherence to rules and after to procedures, and especially emphasizing merit are concepts that continue to be valid today.

2.4 Neo -Classical School

"Classical Management" approach mentioned above, Neo -Classical theory; It focuses on the person, personal behaviors, the factors affecting individual behaviors, social relations and the development of relations within the organization. In this approach, businesses are examined as a social structure or system. According to the Neo-Classical approach, also known as the human relations school or the human relations model, conflict is a natural phenomenon found in all businesses and groups (Cafer, 2011: 256; cited in Barry, 2021: 8-13).

On the other hand, despite the rationality, order and efficiency arguments of the classical theory, the Neo-Classical school has taken the human element as its basis and adopted management based on its characteristics, participation, organizational behavior and motivation, and job satisfaction. This issue continued primarily in the form of human relations approach, organizational behavior and finally human resources management in today's world (Young, 2007: 59; Quoted: Sönmez, 2011:7-16).

It comes to Neo-Classical Theory, the most important name that comes to mind is Elton Mayo. Hawthorne The research of Mayo, a faculty member of Harvard University, who managed an important process of his research, has had a significant role in the development of the "School of Human Relations" (Öztaş, 2017:174-175).

2.4.1 Hawthorne Experiments

The Neo-Classical approach, which is based on proposing that successful results can be obtained if the relations in organizations as a social structure are arranged as needed, especially Hawthorne It has been shaped by the experiments conducted in his research. These studies; "Lighting Experiments" examining the relationship between the lighting of the work

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environment and productivity; The "Relay Assembly Room Experiment", which observes the effect of breaks during work, the incentive wage system and working hours on productivity, and the "Mica Splitting Test Chamber Experiment", which measures the effect of changes in working conditions, and the "Interview Program" applied to the workers in order to investigate the unexpected results and causes of the experiments. ” (Young, 2004: 65 Cited by Sonmez, 2011:8). It is possible to list these experiments as follows (Öztaş, 2017:175):

- *Lighting*
- *Relay assembly room*
- *Second relay assembly room*
- *Mica split test chamber*
- *interview schedule*
- *Serial bonding chamber observations*

Here, it is particularly useful to include the relay assembly room experiment. This experiment: It is important in terms of revealing that social environmental factors rather than physical working conditions are effective on workers. Employees had a positive view of being given freedom, and with this experiment, it was seen that positive social relations between management and workers were effective in increasing productivity (Yıldırım, 2014: 152).

2.4.2 Criticisms of Neo-Classical Management Approach

The main missing aspect of the human relations school is overemphasis on small and informal groups and the relations between these groups, leaving the formal organization and communication in the background. As a result of this, only the human element has been shown in the organizations, and the economic and technical structure of the enterprises, which runs according to the rational rules, has been neglected (Genç, 2007: 51; Quoted: Sönmez, 2011:9).

2.4.3. Evaluation

The basic idea of the neo-classical approach is to understand the employees, that is, the human element within the organization, and to receive help from all the abilities of the human as much as possible. This school is to investigate and examine the relationships between organizational structure and human behavior and to define social groups and their characteristics in the

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organization (Şahin, 2004: 523-547). In this respect, the Neo-Classical school has taken its place in management science with its perspective revealing the importance of the human element for businesses and has also served as a model for research on organizational behavior, group relations, motivation and leadership in the following years.

2.5 Modern School

Another school involved in the development process of management is the Modern School . “Modern Era” theorists pointed to the elements involved in the behavioral origin of humans, as well as the minimization of the elements used in production and quantitative methods ; They saw organizations as an open system and considered management as a center where decisions were made. In the Modern School , there were debates on whether management is an art or a science , and some theories were put forward with extensive research. The most mentioned of these are System Theory and Contingency Theory . On the other hand, Nişancı argued that organizational behavior, management processes and quantitative approach should be included in Modern School Theory , considering Bergeron 's approaches (Nişancı, 2015: 257-294).

2.5.1 System Theory

Systems theory: Although it is an interdisciplinary theory, it is a theorem that has certain limits in terms of internal and external environment and is used to be the whole that interacts with the environment in deciding the inputs and outputs of the system. In other words, the system; It is the sum of the parts that make up it. This approach focuses on the relations and mutual interactions between the parts to understand the whole (Mele, Pels , and Polese , 2010: 126; Quoted by: Akkuş and İzci, 2018:223-237). When systems theory is evaluated from a managerial point of view, it can also be seen that it focuses on management staff. In this respect, systems theory; “It is an approach that creates an organizational structure in which the relationships between sub-systems and their degree of influence on each other come to the fore, problems can be identified with a holistic perspective, and decisions can be taken more effectively by enabling managers to consider organizations as a system” (Tortop, İspir, Aykaç, 1999). : 231-232; Translating: Akkuş and İzci, 2018: 223-237).

In general, researchers divide systems into two branches as open systems that interact with their environment and closed systems that do not (Owens, 1981; cited in: Yalçınkaya, 2002:104-106). Closed systems, as the name suggests, are self-contained structures that are closed to the

outside and do not interact with the environment. For this reason, they are not sensitive to the subject of change (Cole , 1993; cited by Yalçinkaya , 2002:104-106). Despite the low environmental sensitivity of closed systems, environmental sensitivity is continuous in open systems and there is interaction. Therefore, there are inputs and outputs in open systems (Hodgetts , 1975; cited by Yalçinkaya , 2002:104-106). Because of these features, open systems have development, growth and change, and these elements are the reason for the existence of open systems . Open systems give importance to some activities to adapt to their environment. Among these, R&D and marketing activities are important (Cole , 1993; cited by Yalçinkaya, 2002:104-106). Katz and Kahn , on the other hand, state that inputs, transformations and outputs are continuous in open systems.

Figure 2.5.1.1 Open System

Source: Argyris , 1964; Cole , 1993; Sexton , 1970; Hodgetts , 1975; Reported by:
Yalçinkaya, 2002:104-106.

2.5.2 Contingency Theory

According to the Contingency Approach, there is no single best way of activities in organizations. The effectiveness and efficiency of all the methods used vary. In addition, the

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formation of the organization depends on the environmental conditions in which it is found. Contingency theory recommends shaping the structure of the organization according to the connections in external and internal conditions. In other words, the Contingency Approach sees businesses as a system and examines the organization and its relationship with both internal and external factors that affect it (Koçel, 2018:301; cited by Akar, 2019:180-181). The contingency approach has a perspective that, in a sense, replaces the systems approach. The environment, changes in the environment and technology, which are the basis of the differences seen in various approaches and understandings recorded in management in the historical development, have a dominant role. As a result of these changes, the classical period and neo -classical period management approach and then the system approach have been replaced by the contingency point of view. Situational theory, in the environment in which organizations are found; resources, technology, environmental issues, internal and external factors need to be regulated from their own perspective in a way that is compatible (Sucu, 2000:71 Cited by Akar, 2019:180-181).

The contingency approach considers business-organizations as an open system, and the organization's mission, goals, vision , nature of the work and employees, etc. with internal elements; It accepts that it is exposed to external factors such as cultural structure, laws, customers, market and competition conditions. According to this approach, all internal and external conditions should be considered and proper technical methods for management should be decided accordingly. The approach recognizes that the structure of all organizations is unique. For this reason, different analyzes of time, place and conditions must be made according to the enterprises. It is especially important for businesses to be in harmony with their internal and external environments. From this point of view, one of the most important duties of managers is that they must bring this harmony to the top (Güney, 2011: 46).

Figure 2.5.2.2 Organization and Environmental Factors

Source: Güney, 2011.

2.6 Post-Modern Management Theory (Contemporary Management Approaches)

The development of humanistic thought in the globalizing world and the understanding of the importance of the human element in the managerial field in a much more realistic way, modernization in management was needed and a perspective called "Contemporary Management Approaches" or Post-Modern Management Approach by some researchers was adopted. Contemporary management approaches, in which traces of the classical period and neo-classical period are also seen, reflect the change in management science in the 1960s and 1970s, especially in parallel with cyclical developments (Doğan, 2007:188; Quoted by Çil, 2016:13-17). This process is home to the infrastructure of contemporary approaches in management.

It is possible to say that the momentous changes in social, cultural and technological fields, especially in the last quarter of the 20th century, led businesses or organizations to keep up with this change. At this time, organizations had to keep up with the innovations around them by improving their managerial skills. As a result of this, contemporary management approaches have become clear. It would not be wrong to give some of these approaches and the most emphasized ones under the following headings:

- *Total quality Management*
- *Strategic Management*

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- *Resource Dependency Theory*
- *Benchmarking*
- *Reengineering*

In addition to the theorems mentioned above, there are contemporary management approaches such as organizational learning, staff empowerment, population ecology and agency theory, organizational downsizing and organizational empowerment. In this section, Total Quality Management (TQM) is discussed.

2.6.1 Total Quality Management (TQM)

The concept of quality, which is often met in our daily life, is an expression of quality. Although this concept is used in different meanings in parallel with the developments in today's world, it is a quality that affects the future and profitability of businesses. When looking at the definitions in the dictionary, quality; high degree of goodness or excellence. Some researchers define quality as the perfection of the product. Quality of products or services that supply satisfaction beyond the expectations of consumers.

low costs (Halis, 2000:42; Cited by Taner and Kaya, 2005:353-362).

The origin of the word quality is essentially Latin , derived from the word " qualis " and it reflects the desire to reach perfection (Kaya, 2013:3-43; Quoted by: Erdemir, 2015:42-43). The expression of quality, which was first met in the Code of Hammurabi in 1250 BC, includes some criteria that the builder must follow while constructing the house in the relevant law . In addition, a penalty is also mentioned in the law if the construction does not follow the expectations (Bostancı, 2009:12; Quoted by Dolapoğlu , 2018:7).

Today, it is useful to look at the definitions of the institutions in various countries about the concept of quality. For example, the American Society for Quality Control defines quality as a systematic view of achieving excellence . The Japanese Standards Institute, on the other hand, means quality; sees it as a system that produces the product or service in an economical way and responds to the desires of consumers. The British Standards Institute also defines quality as the set of features that distinguish goods or services from others (Johns, 1992, p. 14: Ataran : Taner and Kaya, 2005:353-362).

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Regarding the dimensions of quality, D. Garvin explained some features such as performance, serviceability, aesthetics, suitability, reputation, reliability and durability in his study in 1984 (Çelikaslan , 1996:2; Quoted by Dolapoğlu , 2018:5).

Including their employees, should be approached.

Some principles are among the principles of TQM, such as the integrity of quality, inalienable, inseparable from the element of innovation , requiring teamwork as well as individuality, and that it should be managed on an organizational basis (Altan, 2000; cited in Ağbuga , 2007:5-17).

Possible to analyze it in four distinct parts: Quality Inspection, Quality Control, Quality Assurance and Total Quality Management . While the concepts used during the Quality Inspection (1910) period were clear as nonconformity, elimination, recovery and correction; In the Quality Control (1924) phase or period, the prominent concepts were quality planning, testing, statistics and performance. In the period of Quality Assurance, whose beginning dates to 1950, impact analysis, financial audit and non-production operations came to the fore. The prominent concepts in TQM (1980), which includes the last and fourth stages, are prevention, continuous improvement, leadership, internal customers and performance demonstrations (Dalveard , Kristensenk and Kanji 2007:8; cited by AYU, 2018).

W. Edward Deming , Joseph Juran and Philip Crosby , who have studies on quality management and made significant contributions to this issue , formed the framework of TQM . Under this umbrella Arman V. Feigenbaum and Kaoru It is an accepted fact that Ishikawa also played a role in the development of the concept of quality (Akın, Çetin, & Erol, 1998: 95; cited by Kocamış, 2016:1-21). However, continuous improvement, that is, Kaizen argument , is also in Masaaki . It was developed by Imai and created the philosophy of the Japanese power in both the world economy and quality.

2.6.1.1 Human in Total Quality Management

Demirci (2010: 34; cited by Közleme, 2014:34) states that the approach of TQM includes the love for people . Considering that the working environment is based on the principles of love and respect, it is necessary to give importance to the moral as well as the material needs of the people. In quality management, people should be encouraged, and their needs should always be

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considered. Since quality is a process that concerns all business units, it is a critical issue in employee training.

Deming , who pointed out that management should focus on the human element , opposed this issue by expressing that the scientific management approach in the classical period did not attach importance to this. It is possible to say that Deming , who believes in the necessity of motivation , has similar views with Elton Mayo . According to Deming , customer satisfaction is essential for businesses.

Deming , who included the concepts of research, sales, production and design for businesses in the wheel (Deming Wheel), known by his own name , introduced the PUKÖ Cycle to the Japanese.

PDCA Cycle in Figure 2.6.1.1

TQM have shown that TQM is a factor in the formation and establishment of a quality culture in all organizations where it has a chance to be implemented. In fact, research show that the quality culture plays a role in the sharing of the common values that are constantly developing and improving in the enterprises and strengthens the social relationship between the company employees thanks to trust. It is extremely important to spread a quality culture that prioritizes the satisfaction of both consumers and employees, as it is human-oriented, and to supply innovation and competitive advantage (Kılıç, 2015: 15-16).

Hawthorne Experiments undertook the understanding of the importance of human beings as a human being in working life and the development of human-oriented approaches on this basis. After the Classical School , which sees and thinks human as a machine, this machine metaphor was replaced by human in Neo Classical School , and it reached the top in total quality management.

It is seen that this perspective, which focuses on the human element, has undergone an evolution towards innovation and systems in the interpretation of enterprises . In this cycle, human is the basis of TQM, and the discourse that quality starts with people has also brought to light the Japanese logic's self-view on quality.

3. Conclusion

The history of the concept of management, which can be defined simply as the ability to get people to do business, dates back centuries and is seen even in ancient times. The phenomenon of management, which we saw to have begun to be studied in a much wider and more comprehensive way after the Industrial Revolution, has gained a new identity in parallel with the economic, technological, cultural and social changes in our world, which has become a small village. This identity is primarily that management is a science. Management as a science has continued its development within the path that Taylor started and has further advanced its perspective with the process phenomenon and basic functions (planning, organising, directing, coordination and control) brought by Fayol. Weber, another important name of the classical period management approach, also brought a bureaucratic approach to management. Weber continued his studies focusing on the concepts of rational organization and authority . However, the human element remained in the background in the classical period approaches , including Weber. The Neo-Classical approach, which came right after this period, revealed the importance of the human factor in organizations and announced to the world that issues such as individual and group behavior are effective in productivity, especially with Hawthorne experiments. Modern management, on the other hand, looked at the organizations primarily systematically, argued that the organizations should be considered as a whole with their sub-systems, and with the contingency approach, the necessity of structuring the businesses by considering their own potential was brought to the agenda. Thanks to the Post-Modern

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(Contemporary) approaches after the modern, the environmental factor in the organizations was evaluated together with the employees; It has been seen that management methods such as strategic management, total quality management, resource dependency and benchmarking have been developed. In the relevant part of the study, the importance of the human factor in Total Quality Management was revealed, and it was decided that the quality should be considered not only in terms of products and services, but also in terms of the entire organization. It has been revealed that total quality management is a crucial factor in the formation of a quality culture in enterprises.

4. Resources

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